

The performance of researchers in multidisciplinary research groups: Does social capital matter?

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to discuss the relationship between disciplinary diversity (multidisciplinarity) and the performance of researchers, exploring the moderating role of social capital. The paper contributes to the literature explaining the internal processes within multidisciplinary research units and how they affect scientific performance of researchers. Furthermore, the paper explores the potential moderating role of social capital and how relational dynamics can mitigate the potential problems associated with multidisciplinarity. To test the hypotheses proposed, we performed a quantitative study based on a sample of 155 researchers in the field of management academic. Multiple regression analysis was used in the empirical analysis. The findings suggest that exist a positive relationship between researchers' performance and multidisciplinarity (Inverted U-shaped relationship). Estimations also show that internal social capital moderates this curvilinear relationship, making it possible to achieve higher research performance at higher levels of multidisciplinarity.

Keywords: Diversity, Social Capital, Research, Multidisciplinarity, Researchers performance

1. Introduction

In the organizational and management literature, there is a growing interest in determining whether groups composed of members who are heterogeneous with regard to relational-related and/or job-related attributes obtain better results than groups that are more homogeneous (van Dijk and van Engen, 2013). There are two opposing points of view that rely on social categorization and information/decision-making theories (van Knippenberg et al., 2004) and that can lead to contradictory results. While the former viewpoint suggests that homogeneous groups should perform better with regard to mainly relational-related attributes, the latter suggests that diverse groups have higher performance in relation to job-related attributes (Williams and O'Really, 1998; Joshi and Roh, 2009; Van Knippenberg et al., 2004).

In today's knowledge-based societies, research is carried out largely by groups of researchers (Bozeman et al., 2013). Much scientific research is produced by collaborations among scientists from diverse scientific fields working together with a common goal (Bozeman et al., 2013; Cummings and Kiesler, 2014). Previous papers have shown that scientific collaboration increase productivity and impact of research (Lee and Bozeman, 2005; Bozeman et al., 2013) facilitating knowledge sharing and knowledge transfer (Inkpen and Tsang, 2005; Oh et al., 2005). In the case of academic research groups, papers focusing on the effects of disciplinary diversity on research results show that multidisciplinary groups perform better than less-diverse disciplinary groups (Cummings and Kiesler, 2005; Stvilia et al., 2011), at least up to a certain level of multidisciplinary. Although research group performance is important, the individual performance of members is also a critical research outcome. A key issue is to know how the performance of researchers is affected by belonging to a multidisciplinary research group, an issue on which empirical evidence is quite scarce.

The social capital (SC) literature suggests that SC embedded in social networks influences the knowledge resources available to group members, thus affecting performance (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998; Reagans and Zuckerman, 2001; Chung and Jackson, 2012). In the academic context, some papers emphasize the role of social networks in researcher productivity, focusing on the relational, cognitive and structural SC dimensions (Gonzalez-Brambila, Veloso and Krackhardt, 2013; Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014). However, little is known about how the social capital of research groups moderates the relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance.

The purpose of this paper is to provide an in-depth analysis of the relationship between the multidisciplinary of the members of the research groups and the performance of the

researchers. Additionally, it explores the role played by the SC of research groups in this relationship. To do this, the paper proposes a model that determines the conditions under which multidisciplinary research groups lead to higher researchers' performance. Specifically, the paper suggests that SC moderates this relationship, allowing an increase in the positive effects and mitigating the potential problems of the disciplinary diversity of the members of the research groups.

The empirical analysis was carried out in two steps. First, SC is measured through a questionnaire completed by researchers who attended the 2017 Annual Conference of the European Academy of Management. An exploratory factor analysis was applied to confirm the validity and reliability of the SC scale. Second, diverse econometric estimations have been conducted to test the hypotheses established in the conceptual model.

The contribution of the paper is twofold. First, it contributes to disciplinary diversity and performance research literature providing new evidence on the relationship between the multidisciplinary of groups and researchers' performance. In this sense, the paper tries to shed light on how research groups can take advantage of their disciplinary diversity in order to improve their research performance standards. Second, it contributes to the SC literature by testing the moderating effect of SC in the performance-multidisciplinary relationship. In addition, the paper tries to contribute to the measurement of SC. This construct is usually measured in the academic context drawing on Social Network Techniques. The paper proposes a different measure, applying a scale adapted from the management literature. This approach allows us to deepen the qualitative and behavioural dimensions of SC, which must also be considered to fully understand the internal dynamics within multidisciplinary research groups.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the theoretical background and the related empirical literature on which the proposed model is based. Section 3 describes the applied empirical methodology. It includes the data and the variables used, as well as the factorial analysis. The results are presented in section 4. Section 5 presents the main conclusions, limitations of the study and future lines of research.

2. The role of SC in the performance of multidisciplinary groups

Diversity in the academic research world is a concept that has been widely developed in the field of management (Liu and Xia, 2015). Despite its use, various definitions coexist, and the factors considered for each definition may vary. Some of the traits considered include education and training, personality, gender and age, etc (van Dijk et al., 2012). In general terms, diversity refers to the different characteristics that define the members of a work group (Jackson, Joshi and Erhardt, 2003; Van Knippenberg and Schippers, 2007).

The literature shows confronting perspectives regarding the effects of diversity in teams on performance (van Knippenberg and Mell, 2016; Guillaume et. al., 2017). On the one hand, Williams and O'Reilly (1998) support the idea of a positive influence of heterogeneity given the wider range of abilities, information, and know-how to which the group would have access. Access to broader perspectives favours problem-solving and decision-making processes in diverse teams (Horwitz and Horwitz, 2007; Martín-Alcázar, Romero-Fernández and Sánchez-Gardey, 2011). Furthermore, recent research indicates that openness to diversity in teams could lead to improved performance. Specifically, Luring and Villesèche (2017) and Nielsen and Bøjerson (2019) find this result in a research on gender diversity of teams.

Studies based on social categorization and identity theories (Tajfel and Turner, 1986) and the similarity-attraction paradigm (Byrne, 1971) support the opposite idea. According to those theories, creating a highly diverse group would entail assuming the appearance of subgroups formed by people with similar traits, which would hinder the overall performance of the group (Van Dijk et al., 2012). Research has shown that people tend to identify and collaborate with people who share similar characteristics and values, which helps them to avoid discrepancies and possible disagreements as regards the development of ideas (Lungeanu and Contractor, 2015). In societies characterised by high collectivism, the stress on belonging leads to the identification of people as in-group or out-of-group (Hofstede, 2011). Nevertheless, this reasoning also applies to the general behaviour of people. According to Janssen and Huang (2008), individuals tend to cooperate with other individuals who share their same social identity because they are considered part of the same group. In fact, it seems that difference with some individuals increases people's perception of social identity and creates stronger bonds with in-group individuals. At the same time, according to Guillaume et al. (2012) such differentiation lowers group members' trust and cooperation with those that are not part of their group. All in all, the results of the study by Randel and Jaussi (2003) suggest that the performance of the group and of the individual are influenced by social and personal identities.

Diversity regarding factors that define relationships, like race, age or gender, may have a negative effect on team performance due to their importance for social categorisation (Williams and O'Reilly, 1998). That is, these factors are the basis for social identity; diverse social identities within a group may lead to feelings of distrust or to uncooperative behaviours, hence its impact on performance. In contrast, diversity of traits related to work, such as education, affect team performance positively possibly because these traits condition team processes concerned with creation, although this effect is highly complex. That is, a suitable integration and management of cognitive diversity seems to be necessary in reducing the negative impact on team performance (Williams and O'Reilly, 1998).

Research has focused on different factors for exploring the effects of cognitive diversity on performance. In particular, Chi, Huang and Lin (2009) analysed tenure diversity and found a positive relationship between organizational tenure diversity and innovation of the team. Similarly, Mitchell et al. (2017) found that cognitive diversity in research teams led to debate, which in turn led to innovation. In addition, Wang, Kim and Lee (2016) found that cognitive diversity is related to team creativity and motivation. Tsai et al. (2014), on the other hand, suggested a positive quadratic relationship between knowledge heterogeneity and innovation. Studies of the effects of functional background yielded inconclusive results (Mello and Rentsch, 2015). Finally, team members' educational level and education type received have opposite effects on performance (Curseu et al., 2012; Cummings, Kiesler, Zadeh and Balakrishnan, 2013). While educational level diversity has negative effects on performance, diversity as regards specialisation is found to affect performance of teams in a positive way.

Cognitive diversity as regards scholars' disciplines allegedly enhances team performance (Salazar et al., 2012). Van Knippenberg, van Ginkel, and Homan (2013) and Jackson, Joshi, and Erhardt (2003) identify team diversity regarding specialization with team success. Zuo and Zhao (2018) point out that multidisciplinary teams does not seem to enhance the number of collaborations, however, Cummings and Kiesler (2005) indicate that a high interdisciplinarity in teams enhances performance outcomes regarding research but stress the importance of coordination. Porac et al.'s (2004) comparison between multidisciplinary teams and homogeneous teams on scientific collaboration indicates that high diversity regarding disciplines increases the amount of published research. In fact, this idea is supported by Stvilia (2011). Nevertheless, the wider social network available to diverse teams and their enhanced productivity may have some drawbacks such as the problems resulting from lack of cohesion, that is, conflict or cooperation and identification issues (Perry-Smith and Vincent, 2008).

The above discussion suggests that multidisciplinary could have a curvilinear rather a linear effect on research performance. In other words, cognitive diversity would have a positive effect on knowledge creation and productivity; however, once the threshold is crossed, diversity would have a negative influence on productivity derived from conflicts and coordination costs (Cummings and Kiesler, 2005; Yong et al., 2014).

Thus, the first hypothesis is as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There exists a positive and increasing relationship between the level of multidisciplinary of academic groups and the researchers' performance, with a maximum from which the effect is inverse.

The SC literature suggests that the structure and configuration of social networks affects the knowledge resources available to the members of the group and, therefore, to their performance (Reagans and Zuckerman, 2001; Chung and Jackson, 2012). Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1988) introduced the SC concept in the management literature. Their definition resembles significantly that which was provided by Bordieu, differentiating between three dimensions of SC: *relational*, *cognitive* and *structural*. These dimensions are interrelated and provide the basis for knowledge transfer and consider trust and common viewpoints as necessary conditions for the correct development of these networks.

Literature on the relational dimension shows the paramount importance of factors such as trust for cooperation (Adler and Kwon, 2002; Choi, 2015; Pardo et al., 2006). Therefore, relationships between individuals must comply with norms of behaviour based on reciprocity expectations among other factors (Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014; Schram and Charness, 2015). The cognitive dimension deals with cognition and involves shared beliefs and codes that enable communication (language), hence knowledge transfer, and the setting of common goals, thus enhancing collaboration and cooperation (Chow and Chan, 2008; Tsai and Ghoshal, 1998). In the same vein, when collaborating members have common goals, responsibility and integrity are more easily developed (Leana and Pil, 2006). The structural dimension draws on common ties and relationships that link the members of a group (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998) and allow the access to the resources offered by participants in the network. In contrast, the first two dimensions are more related to members' ability for knowledge transfer (Andrews, 2010).

An alternative classification of the components of SC distinguishes between its internal and external dimensions, focusing on the structure of the network (Woolcock and Narayan, 2000).

The internal (or *bonding*) SC comprises resources inherent to the relations among actors within the collective; while the external (or *bridging*) dimension refers to the external relations that actors maintain with other actors (Adler and Kwon, 2002). In this regard, Chung and Jackson (2012) suggest that both types of relationships have a positive influence on performance. Similarly, Oh et al. (2006) highlight that group effectiveness is maximized through optimal configurations of intragroup closure relationships and horizontal and vertical bridge relationships. As Adler and Kwon (2002) point out, the definition of SC of Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) focuses on both internal and external linkages.

Despite the scarcity of research on SC related to the academy, this section provides an overview of the main contributions. Siadat et al. (2012) found knowledge creation is positively influenced by SC and organizational culture. Steinmo (2015) analyses the role of SC on firm-university collaboration and identifies a positive influence of relative SC on the effectiveness of these collaborations. In addition, the author points out that shared goals exert a cohesive effect on members of the network and their collaboration. Gonzalez-Brambila (2014) indicate that the productivity of scientists increases if they are at the centre of their publishing network and according to the diversity of cognitive capital available to him or her, but this situation may vary depending on the researcher's discipline. Regarding the output of the collaborations, relational ties explain the quality of the publications but not the impact of the studies, while interdisciplinary collaborations yield high-impact research outputs. The structural dimension is also explained by Gonzalez-Brambila et al., (2013) who suggest that citation impact is positively affected by structural holes. Similarly, citation impact and publications are also positively influenced by structural SC (Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila, 2016). In the same vein, the citation impact of researchers is positively affected by average tie strength, efficiency and centrality (Abbasi, Altmann and Hossain, 2011), as it is indirectly affected by cognitive SC and author productivity (Li, Liao and Yen, 2013).

Multidisciplinary research groups through SC of group's members can access to diverse information that could complement research groups' skills and generate new ideas for research based on a greater scope of skills (Gonzalez-Brambila, Veloso and Krackhardt, 2013; Perry-Smith and Vincent, 2008; Gonzalez-Brambila, 2014). Nevertheless, diversity of backgrounds may generate barriers for collaboration such as misunderstandings due to differences in language, culture or viewpoints, as well as lack of cooperation due to integration conflicts, with a potential negative influence on performance (Perry-Smith and Vincent, 2008). All these problems may be solved by constant interaction, which serves to establish solid ties based on trust. Therefore, higher identification and trust between collaborating members would increase knowledge sharing and cooperation in knowledge creation (Yu, 2018; García-Sánchez et al.,

2019). In turn, the increased trust would facilitate problem solving.

Based on the review of previous literature on group diversity, the paper proposes a conceptual model in which relationship between researcher's performance and the multidisciplinary of research group is established (Figure 1). It is expected that researchers who belong to research groups with greater multidisciplinary perform better than researchers who belong to groups with less diversity of disciplines. On the other hand, Lee, Walsh and Wang (2015) indicate that the size of the diverse team has a positive relationship with the probability of publishing high-impact studies. Notwithstanding this, these positive effects may be limited. Research shows that productivity of large diverse teams whose members come from different academic backgrounds is lower (Cummings et al., 2013), and the positive influence of size on collaboration becomes a negative effect on creativity after a threshold is crossed (Lavie and Drodi, 2012). The positive effects of team diversity are also limited regarding the depth of information use. Allegedly, when a team reaches a certain level of diversity, the positive effects of size on information use decline (Dahlin, Weingart and Hinds, 2005).

Figure 1. Conceptual model

The literature suggests that a complete analysis of the effects of diversity on performance requires the use of additional variables regarding the unit conditions. Thus, direct models are not appropriate. The use of moderating variables includes variables related to the institution or the context (Van Dijk et al., 2012).

This study proposes the use of SC as a variable that moderates the relationship between multidisciplinary and researcher's performance. Drawing on previous research, the paper explores how SC could allow team members to benefit from the disciplinary diversity of their

research group improving their research performance. It is expected that the relational, cognitive and structural dimensions of SC have a moderating effect on the performance of researchers in contexts of high disciplinary diversity.

Thus, the second hypothesis is as follows:

Hypothesis 2: Social capital embedded in research groups positively moderates the relationship between multidisciplinary and scientific performance of researchers.

3. Empirical framework

3.1 Data

To test the hypotheses described above, we performed a quantitative study based on a sample of scholars in the field of management. The questionnaire was pretested through a sample of researchers belonging to the discipline who received the questionnaire by email and provided feedback. To enhance the questionnaire, all the suggestions were added in the final version. As a first step, a self-response questionnaire was delivered to researchers attending the annual conference of the European Academy of Management (EURAM). We choose this congress because it is a benchmark in the field of management due to its international character and their high degree of diversity. The questionnaire was specifically designed to measure issues related to researchers' SC, as well as some aspects of their respective scientific collaborations and some information related to university, country, research experience, etc. Responding researchers were informed about the purpose of the study. Although 155 identified questionnaires were obtained, forty-five scholars in the initial sample had to be removed because they either could not be identified in Scopus, or had no publication records. Therefore, the final number of usable questionnaires was 110.

In addition to the individual information extracted from the questionnaire, for scholars we obtained information about their respective research networks in order to measure their multidisciplinary levels. A scholar's network is defined as the group formed by him/her and all their co-authors in Scopus ranked publications

3.2 Variables

The dependent variable in our model is *Researcher performance*. For evaluating research performance there exist different measures such as publications, citations, etc., that are used in empirical literature. In our study, we opted to use Scopus' indicator known as h-index

(Hirsch, 2005). Hirsch defines the h-index as ‘a scientist has an h-index if h of his or her N_p papers have at least h citations each, and the other $(N_p - h)$ papers have $\leq h$ citations each’ (Hirsch, 2005, p. 16569). This indicator has received criticism because it does not take into account the length of the scientific career, the effect of co-authorship or the journal quality (Kelly and Jennions, 2006; Batista et al., 2006; Hirsch, 2010). However, the main advantage of this indicator and why it has been widely used in the academic context is that it combines a measure of the quantity and impact of publications in a single indicator (Huang, 2012).

The independent variables included are the following:

-Multidisciplinarity. To assess the degree of multidisciplinarity, we focused on the research group built by each focal scholar and all his/her respective co-authors. We used Blau’s (1977) index of validity which is a heterogeneity measure traditionally adopted by the literature on workforce diversity (Pitts, 2005) to operationalize multidisciplinarity. It is calculated as $[1 - \sum p_i^2]$, where p is the proportion of researchers in the respective discipline and i is the number of disciplines represented in the academic research group. The multidisciplinarity index ranges from 0 to 1; values close to 1 indicate greater multidisciplinarity (Pitts, 2005). For each researcher, Scopus provides information on the number of papers published in each of the possible 27 subject areas, ordering them from highest to lowest frequency. Within of a research group to identify scholar’ and co-authors’ disciplinary affiliation, each researcher was ascribed to a research field through a variable built by concatenating the two Scopus areas in which he/she had published more. This artificial variable was created to ensure variance, considering that the study was focused on the management discipline. In total, eighty-eight new disciplines were identified in the network.

-Social capital. Given the lack of specific instruments to measure SC in the academic context, we opted to develop our own scale, adapting the items proposed by Chow and Chan (2008). To assess the relational, cognitive and structural dimensions of SC, as proposed by Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), we designed a set of seven-point Likert scale items, ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (7) (see questionnaire in Appendix I). The wording of the indicators was based on previous empirical research, and it was carefully pretested by a group of scholars in the field of management.

-Control variables. To reduce potential omitted variable bias, a set of plausibly relevant control variables were included in the empirical analysis. Specifically, we controlled for the size of the research group (*size*) because of its potential effect on research productivity (Cumming et al., 2013). To identify research groups in the paper we focused on the co-

authorship network of each academic, considering publications in the 2000-2016 period. With this, we followed the output-based method proposed by Cohen (1991), which does not consider formal affiliation, but collaborations between members of the group. Additionally, we controlled for the years of research experience (*experience*) (Lee and Bozeman, 2005) with the objective of considering for the duration of academics' career when assessing their respective h-indexes. To measure this variable, a specific question was included in the questionnaire.

3.3 Factorial analysis

With the exploratory analysis, we intended to confirm validity and reliability of SC scale and to verify the internal structure of the construct, checking whether the dimensions proposed in the previous literature are relevant in the specific field of academic research. Following the commonly used rules, eigenvalues near or greater than 1.0 were used to select the factors to be used in the analysis. To define each of the retained factors, we kept items with loads higher than 0.50 in a single factor. The adequacy of factor analysis in our dataset was confirmed using Bartlett's test of sphericity (significance value < 0.05) and the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure of sampling adequacy ($0.829 > 0.70$). The value obtained for Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each of the factors extracted confirmed the reliability of the data collection, as well as inter-item correlations for the variables in the survey. Results for all these analyses are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Exploratory Factor Analysis Results

Items	Component (factor loadings)		
	1	2	3
In my research team, the research members usually ...			
... maintain contacts and collaborations with colleagues within the same field of research	0.825		
... obtain joint research results with colleagues within the same field of research (e.g. research projects or theses)	0.812		
... maintain a good social climate	0.784		
... attend seminars, conferences or workshops in our field	0.701		
... exchange ideas and share knowledge and information	0.660		
... interact frequently and easily with one another	0.640		
... obtain joint research results with colleagues from other fields of research (e.g. research projects or theses)		0.892	
... maintain contacts and collaborations with colleagues from other fields of research		0.859	
... partner with management professionals to develop research processes		0.629	
... hold regular formal meetings			0.822
... hold frequent informal meetings			0.659
Eigenvalues	4.931	1.780	0.944
Total variance explained by each factor (%)	44.825	16.183	8.580
Cumulative variance explained by the factors (%)	44.825	61.009	69.59
Cronbach's alpha	0.883	0.777	0.635
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin: 0.829			
Bartlett's test of sphericity: Chi-square: 590.104 gl : 55 Signification: 0.000			

***significant at 1%; Varimax rotation was used to simplify the interpretation of the factors

From the exploratory factor analysis, three factors were obtained. Factor 1 was labelled *internal SC*, and contained items related to relational and cognitive SC embedded in relations with colleagues in the same field of research. Factor 2 was labelled *external SC*, and included items associated with cognitive and relational SC embedded in relations either with colleagues outside the field or with professionals. Factor 3 was labelled *structural SC*. It is comprised of two items associated with the patterns of connections among research group members. Observing the nature of the three factors extracted, we conclude that they support the expected categorization of SC into relational, cognitive and structural dimensions. However, they also highlight that SC flows through intragroup social bonds and bridging relationships. Therefore, the results of our factor analysis show that both classifications of SC overlap. In fact, the heterogeneity of research group members in relation to their main disciplines emphasizes the importance of bridging relationships for relational and cognitive SC resources (external SC). But, on the other hand, homogeneous subgroups (formed by researchers from the same discipline) can also be found within research groups, making closure relationships predominant for relational and cognitive SC (internal SC). Figure 2 illustrates the factors, showing how they link with these categories.

Figure 2. Interactions between SC dimensions

Source: Own elaboration

4. Results

The extracted factors were introduced together with the rest of variables into multiple regression models as interaction terms, with the objective of testing the hypotheses established in section 2. Table 2 shows the maximum and minimum values, means, standard deviations and correlations of the variables introduced in further analyses. These figures show that the average size of research groups is 8 members; the researchers have an average h-index of 4, and an average research experience of roughly 14 years. The average level of diversity in disciplinary categories within groups is 0.51, in a 0-1 scale.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and correlations

Variable	Max	Min	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1 H-Index	23	0	4.173	5.106	1						
2 Team size	60	2	8.130	8.996	0.048	1					
3 Experience	50	2	14.730	9.677	0.569**	0.045	1				
4 Multidisciplinarity	0.95	0	0.513	0.362	0.052	0.106	0.068	1			
5 Internal social capital (factor)			0	1	0.070	-0.215*	0.055	-0.281**	1		
6 External social capital (factor)			0	1	-0.170	0.037	-0.022	-0.305**	0	1	
7 Structural social capital (factor)			0	1	-0.027	-0.138	-0.009	-0.460**	0	0	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level; * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Four models were estimated (Table 3). Model 1 shows the isolated effect of the two control variables (*experience* and *team size*) on the dependent variable (h-index). The variable measuring scholars' years of experience was significant and positively related to performance.

This result could be explained by the definition of the h-index, which is an accumulative measure that tends to grow as the number of publications of the researchers increases.

To test the effect of multidisciplinary on researchers performance two models were estimated (Models 2 and 3). Model 2 shows that the linear term of the *multidisciplinarity* variable has the expected sign but it is not significant. The result dramatically changes when the quadratic term of the multidisciplinary variable (*multidisciplinarity*²) is introduced. As can be observed in Model 3, in this case, *multidisciplinarity* turns out to be significant, showing a positive effect on scientific performance of researchers, as previous studies have also found (e.g. Porac et al., 2004; Cummings and Kiesler, 2005). The estimated coefficient β for the quadratic term (*multidisciplinarity*²) is negative but significant, confirming that the effects of this variable on researchers' h-indexes can be depicted as an inverted U-shaped relationship. As the relation between multidisciplinary and h-index is nonlinear, the effect on h-index of a change in multidisciplinary depends on the value of multidisciplinary. The marginal effects are linearly decreasing, making the h-index grow to a point where the marginal effects begin to be negative. The results support Hypothesis 1, showing that h-index is reduced when the discipline diversity is increased over a certain level. This result is in line with previous papers that found a curvilinear relationship between cognitive diversity and performance (De Saá-Pérez et al., 2015; Yegros-Yegros et al., 2015).

To test the second hypothesis, *internal SC*, *external SC* and *structural SC* (factors extracted) were introduced as moderators of the relationship between multidisciplinary and researchers' performance (Model 4). The estimation of the last regression model confirmed that only the interaction term to measure the moderating effect of *internal SC* was significant. Therefore, we find evidence that the relational and cognitive SC of research group between members of the same field positively moderates the curvilinear relationship between multidisciplinary and research performance, making the optimum reached with higher levels of disciplinary diversity. This result partially confirms hypothesis 2 that to mitigate the conflict and communicational problems appearing as multidisciplinary increases, research groups should foster frequent and smooth interactions among members, building a collaborative climate that facilitates the exchange of ideas and knowledge sharing. This internal SC seems to be more relevant, according to the results of the regression analysis, than the establishment of formal co-ordination mechanisms, or the development of external collaborations.

Table 3. Results of the regression analysis

Variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
Constant		(0.835)		(0.979)		(1.077)		(1.071)
Experience	0.567***	(0.042)	0.566***	(0.043)	0.515***	(0.044)	0.465**	(0.045)
Team Size	0.020	(0.049)	0.019	(0.05)	-0.006	(0.049)	0.027	(0.05)
Multidisciplinarity			0.012	(1.138)	1.202**	(7.448)	1.419***	(7.538)
Multidisciplinarity ²					-1.199**	(7.774)	-1.366**	(7.825)
Multidisciplinarity × Internal SC							0.170*	(0.687)
Multidisciplinarity × External SC							-0.016	(0.628)
Multidisciplinarity × Structural SC							0.098	(0.696)
R ²	0.322		0.323		0.355		0.382	
Durbin-Watson							1.472	
Overall F	25.457***		16.823***		14.427***		8.998***	

N = 110. Standardized regression coefficients are report, standard errors are in parentheses. **p* < 0.1, ** *p* < 0.05, *** *p* < 0.01

5. Conclusions and Discussion

Diverse groups are becoming more plentiful in organizations, and universities are no exception. Research is increasingly carried out in large research groups, and in many cases, these groups are composed of researchers from different disciplines (Bozeman et al., 2013; Cummings and Kiesler, 2014). This multidisciplinarity is a response to the challenges of today's societies, where integrated knowledge occupies a predominant position, as a source of economic growth and productivity (OECD, 1996). Literature on research teams has highlighted the importance of group processes and the influence of group characteristics for research group productivity (Wang, 2016). A key element is to know how the internal processes are developed within the multidisciplinary research groups in a way that leads to greater research results of researchers.

This paper addresses this issue by analysing the multidisciplinarity-performance relationship drawing on a sample of research groups within the field of management. The paper finds that the relationship between multidisciplinarity and the performance of researchers is nonlinear. That is, as disciplinary diversity increases, research results improve until multidisciplinarity reaches an optimum level, at which point the researchers' performance decreases. This suggests that, when a certain level of multidisciplinarity is reached, some difficulties arise, related to the lack of cohesion as well as conflict, cooperation and identification problems (Perry-Smith and Vincent, 2008). Thus, an additional interesting issue that exceeds the scope of this study would be to determine the level of multidisciplinarity at which the positive effects of disciplinary diversity begin to diminish.

The productivity of the researchers depends on diverse variables, including the size of the group, the experience of the researchers, or the researchers' SC, as previous literature has shown (Cumming et al., 2013; Rodriguez and Gonzalez-Brambila, 2016). The paper proposes a conceptual model in which the effect of multidisciplinary on the results of the researchers would be conditioned by the SC that the researchers bring to the group. In the paper, SC is measured through a scale, trying to obtain deeper qualitative and behavioural information about this multidimensional construct. From the exploratory factorial analysis three factors emerged, supporting the need to differentiate between the relational, cognitive and structural SC dimensions. Additionally, the factor analysis provides new insights on the internal and external SC dimensions distinguishing between the relational and cognitive SC embedded in relations with colleagues within the same research field (internal SC), and the relational and cognitive SC located in relations outside the research field (external SC). This result indicates that multidisciplinary groups may be fragmented into different subgroups formed by researchers belonging to the same field, affecting internal dynamics and, therefore, collective performance.

As the empirical analysis has confirmed, not all the dimensions of SC help to manage internal dynamics within multidisciplinary research groups. The moderating effect seems to be limited to the relationships established between academics from the same discipline. The results are not significant in relation to contacts external to the field, which do not seem to affect internal dynamics. Similarly, the result obtained for the structural dimension of SC shows that the term of interaction is not significant. The mere organization of formal or informal meetings and other spaces for encounters among collaborators does not appear by itself to reduce potential task conflict or communication difficulties.

From the perspective of the managers of the research groups, it seems fair to recommend the implementation of human resource practices that attract for collaboration researchers whose knowledge and skills are better adapted to the needs of the group in order to increase the disciplinary diversity of the research group. Practices that facilitate collaboration should be encouraged, thus strengthening cooperation among group members, which is linked to trust and knowledge-sharing. In this way, the performance of researchers could be increased and multidisciplinary research groups could achieve better performance.

Finally, notice that the research design proposed in this paper, based on a self-response survey to measure SC, has provided an interesting insight into the internal dynamics of multidisciplinary research groups, but a deeper empirical analysis would be necessary to

understand fully the structure of relationships between academics from different disciplines. Future research should be done to overcome some limitations of the paper. SC is measured through respondents' perceptions of trust and cooperation within a research group; therefore, to capture a more complete picture of SC, surveys could be administered to all members of the research group. Likewise, the sample is based on researchers in the field of management, so the study should be extended to other scientific fields to test if the internal dynamics of the research groups are field dependent. Since there may be an inverse causality between SC and the performance of researchers, the mechanisms that explain the effect of interaction could be conditioned by this fact. A deeper analysis of this influence should be carried out in future research.

The conclusions of our study invite future research that could extend and contrast the findings obtained here. Social Network Analysis could provide interesting tools for this purpose, to describe and represent the social structures of different research fields. Therefore, it might be interesting to perform future analyses designed to compare both methodologies. This would allow us to deepen on the objective and subjective aspects of SC, showing which is the more appropriate way to measure the construct in each circumstance. Finally, diversity is a multifaceted construct (Tasheva and Hillman, 2019) so future research should also address how the disciplinary diversity of research groups interacts with individual-level diversity, and its impact on research results.

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Appendix 1: Questionnaire of social capital

We request that you give us your opinion on a series of questions related to your activity as a researcher belonged to a research team.

It will take no more than 5 minutes. All the data you provide us will be treated in an aggregated and anonymous way, with strictly academic objectives, so your answers will be completely confidential.

Researcher information		
Name:		
University:		
Gender:	Position:	Scientific field:
Years of research experience:		

Please indicate your degree of agreement with the following statements:

	<i>Strongly disagree</i>					<i>Strongly agree</i>	
	1	2	3	4	5		
In my research team, the research members usually ...							
...maintain contacts and collaborations with colleagues within the same field of research	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...interact frequently and easily with one another	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...maintain contacts and collaborations with colleagues from other fields of research	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...attend seminars, conferences or workshops in our field	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...exchange ideas and share knowledge and information	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...obtain joint research results with colleagues within the same field of research (e.g. research projects or theses)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...obtain joint research results with colleagues from other fields of research (e.g. research projects or theses)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...maintain a good social climate	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...hold frequent informal meetings	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...hold regular formal meetings	<input type="checkbox"/>						
...partner with management professionals to develop research processes	<input type="checkbox"/>						